

Study of Stress at Workplace for the Members of Chhattisgarh Society of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technology at Raipur, Chhattisgarh

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ABSTRACT

Chronic job stress is brought on by circumstances that are detrimental to an employee's performance and/or general physical and mental health. To help us to get a better understanding of the "Study of stress at workplace for the members of Chhattisgarh Society of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technology at Raipur, Chhattisgarh. To help the members of CGSPST better comprehend the circumstances and gather their responses, a well-structured questionnaire was created. The purpose of the research is to examine the stressors that affect the members of the CGSPST in Raipur, Chhattisgarh, as well as to assess employee stress levels and provide recommendations for reducing them. The method used to analyze the data was descriptive analysis. For data analysis, Excel and SPSS v20 were the software utilized. The poll has a sample size of 65. The study enables us to see that stress can be caused by the workplace, social groups, and an individual's personal life in equal measure. The participants need to practice time management and participate in a variety of social activities to lessen the stress in their lives. Sometimes tension can be decreased by meditation. A person can de-stress by talking about their despair or anxiety. Consequently, implementing fundamental stress management strategies has a significant impact on the organization's productivity.

Keywords: Chronic Stress, Organizational Stressor, Individual Stressor, CGSPST, Raipur

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Stress has been defined in many ways according to Schuler (1980), "Stress is a dynamic condition in which an individual is confronted with an opportunity, constraints or demand related to what he or she desires and for which the outcome is perceived to be both uncertain and important".

Stress may be defined as the reaction people have to excessive pressures or other types of demands placed on them.

Job stress is a condition arising from the interaction of people and their jobs and is characterized by changes within the people that force them to deviate from their normal functioning (Beehr and Newman, 1978).

The most commonly accepted definition of Stress (mainly attributed to Richard S Lazarus) is that stress is a condition or feeling experienced when a person perceives that "demands exceed the personal and social resources the individual can mobilize."

Feelings of tension, nervousness, impatience, tiredness, anxiety, sleeplessness, and various illnesses can be subjective perceptions of stress. It may also be considered an imbalance- real or perceived- between an individual's resources or capabilities and the demands placed upon them.

Stress has three primary causes: environmental, organizational, and personal.

Conditions that are seen as hazardous or difficult about past experiences and the resources available to you are known as stressors. There are two types of stressors: internal and external. The environment of an individual is the source of external stressors. These could include receiving negative feedback from someone else, losing one's job, or experiencing a relative's death. Internal stressors originate from within an individual. Most of our emotional problems, such as anger, sadness, fear, guilt, frustration, and shame, are mental creations.

Stress management

Stress management is the cognitive understanding of the factors that contribute to stress and the techniques for removing stress from the body safely and healthily. It is also a collection of methods used by experts to assist us in managing different types of stress. It is a collection of abilities that help people deal with challenging circumstances in a more efficient manner, which helps them feel better emotionally, behave better, and frequently feel more in

control. Stress is described as a person's physiological reaction to internal or external stimuli that sets off the fight-or-flight response. Stress management strategies are designed to provide an individual with useful coping mechanisms for handling psychological stress.

Importance of stress management

Stress management teaches a person how to keep a good outlook and how to regulate their emotions so that others won't perceive them as overreacting. A positive outlook can help you finish any activity quickly. Identifying stress sources is the first stage in stress management; the next step is to understand how to help modify the situation. Most of the time, we just have to learn to accept things as they are. Occasionally, we can solve the issue. On the other hand, less time may be spent addressing the causes. By extending the task hour or assigning it to someone else, he or she can also find measures to lower their stress levels. Understanding the sources of stress and one's own emotional and physical reactions to it is important. Many cultures use stress management techniques to assist people gain self-control. Everyone experiences stress at some point in their lives, and it is difficult for everyone. On the other hand, stress can have negative repercussions that make it difficult for a person to live a productive life.

At the core of it all is mind over mind. In addition to believing that one can do everything by the deadline, one must also possess self-discipline. Discipline is the first step in stress management since one needs to learn how to both calm down and handle all that is thrown at them. Everybody has their breaking moments. The challenging aspect is learning to restrain our thoughts and emotions so that we don't overreact. Everyone should therefore become knowledgeable about stress management. Each person experiences this state differently, yet the general idea remains the same. To effectively practice it, a person must identify something that helps them let go of all of their concerns.

1.2 Objectives of the study

To study the stress factors on the members of CGSPST, Raipur.

To analyze the stress level of the members of CGSPST, Raipur.

To study the correlation between the variables of organizational stressors, group stressors, and individual stressors.

1.3 Research Methodology

Modern life is full of stress. Stress on individuals ranges from personal day-to-day life to their organizational activities. Urbanization, industrialization, and an increase in the scale of operations in society are causing increasing stress. In this changing environment, participation, interaction, transaction, planning, and regulation become key issues, each with its frustrations. People feel stress, as they no longer have complete control over what happens in life. There is no escape from stress in modern life. In today's context, Stress is a costly business expense that affects both employee health and company profits (Find and Otte, 1994). Thus, it becomes very important to understand the causes of stress, and its impact and adopt strategies for minimizing its impact. The present study concentrates on the causes of stress as well as its impact on the members. We can see that there are numerous conditions in which people may feel stress. Conditions that tend to cause stress are called stressors. Although even a single stressor may cause major stress usually stressors combine to press an individual in a variety of ways until stress develops. For the present study, stressors have been classified into three groups namely, organizational, group, and individual factors. All these factors are considered to be important factors in causing stress in an individual. From the literature review, it is seen that there are no studies done on the relationship between these stressors in the Raipur city which left the gap and there is a need to study the same. It is considered that if in any of the factors the employee had conflict or faced pressure; it may affect his performance adversely which in turn affects the productivity of the organization.

The scope of this study is limited to the Members of The Chhattisgarh Society of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technology, Raipur, Chhattisgarh.

The method used for the sampling technique is the non-probability census sampling inquiry method. A complete enumeration of all items in the population is known as a census inquiry. I did my research in Raipur, Chhattisgarh Society of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technology. Since the sample design is a census inquiry, the number of members at the office is 70, but due to the non-availability of 5 members, the population size has been reduced to 65. Therefore, the study consists of 65 members. The source of the data for the study has been through primary and secondary methods. This is the data source that is collected firsthand. This data was collected from the members or individuals or respondents through a questionnaire for further analysis. Further information was collected from the articles available in websites and books for attaining clarity on the subject of Stress. There are various methods of collecting primary data, particularly in surveys and descriptive research. In this project, the "questionnaire method" the members of the Chhattisgarh Society of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technology were asked to fill up a questionnaire. The tool that has been used for data analysis is Excel V13 and SPSS 20.

1.4 Data Analysis and Findings

The purpose of this questionnaire was to measure the level of Stress faced by the members at "The Chhattisgarh Society of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technology", Raipur. The questionnaire is represented in a set of 28 questions (including the demographics) with five options given and the respondent has to tick the answer which he/she feels appropriate. Sixty-five members from various technical fields have responded to the questionnaire. Each question is used to reveal certain information that will reflect the level of stress the members face. The questionnaire is divided into four parts, which are the various factors used to measure the level of stress at work. Therefore, the analysis is done at these levels. These factors are Demographics, Organizational

Stressors, Group Stressors, and Individual Stressors. The five-point Likert scale is used in the study from 0 to 4, naming Strongly Disagree as 0 followed by Disagree as 1, Neutral as 2, Agree as 3, and Strongly Agree as 4.

Table 1 - Descriptive Analysis of Demographics

S. No.	Measures	Description	N (%)
1	VAR00001- Gender	Male	34 (52.3%)
		Female	31 (47.7%)
2	VAR00002-Age	Less than 25 years	8 (12.3%)
		25 to30 years	19 (29.2%)
		30 to 35 years	19 (29.2%)
3	VAR00003-Marital Status	Above 35 years	19 (29.2%)
		Married	58 (89.2%)
		Unmarried	7 (10.8%)
4	VAR00004-Qualification	Graduate	11 (16.9%)
		Post Graduate	54 (83.1%)
5	VAR00005- Competitive pressures are a reason of stress within the organization.	Strongly Disagree	14 (21.5%)
		Disagree	5 (7.7%)
		Neutral	3 (4.6%)
		Agree	33 (50.8%)
		Strongly Agree	10 (15.4%)
6	VAR00006- Inability to voice complaints frustrates me.	Disagree	22 (33.8%)
		Neutral	24 (36.9%)
		Agree	17 (26.2%)
		Strongly Agree	2 (3.1%)
7	VAR00007- My job description is unrealistic.	Disagree	20 (30.8%)
		Neutral	31 (47.7%)
		Agree	14 (21.5%)
8	VAR00008- Communication within my organization is not effective	Disagree	34 (52.3%)
		Neutral	16 (24.6%)
		Agree	15 (23.1%)
9	VAR00009- If a project I am working on fails, I tend to brood over the failure for a long time.	Strongly Disagree	11 (16.9%)
		Disagree	49 (75.4%)
10	VAR00010- If a project I am working on fails, I learn from the experience and move on to the next job.	Neutral	5 (7.7%)
		Agree	50 (76.9%)
		Strongly Agree	15 (23.1%)
11	VAR00011- Poor lighting and ventilation, a crowded work area causes interference with my work.	Strongly Disagree	10 (15.4%)
		Disagree	8 (12.3%)
		Neutral	7 (10.8%)
		Agree	40 (61.5%)

		Neutral	1 (1.5%)
12	VAR00012- I have someone at work or outside it who I can confide in.	Agree	42 (64.6%)
		Strongly Agree	22 (33.8%)
13	VAR00013- Lack of cohesiveness within the group brings about difficulty in getting a particular job done.	Agree	45 (69.2%)
		Strongly Agree	20 (30.8%)
		Disagree	12 (18.5%)
14	VAR00014- Ill will within the group members/ towards me causes stress, which reflects in my work.	Neutral	27 (41.5%)
		Agree	26 (40%)
		Strongly Disagree	8 (12.3%)
15	VAR00015- My group depends on me so much at work that I have to do it all.	Disagree	5 (7.7%)
		Neutral	41 (63.1%)
		Agree	11 (16.9%)
		Disagree	15 (23.1%)
16	VAR00016- If others would just consider my opinion, we could solve most of our problems.	Neutral	22 (33.8%)
		Agree	28 (43.1%)
		Disagree	47 (72.3%)
17	VAR00017- I have little patience with my coworkers.	Neutral	18 (27.7%)
		Disagree	11 (16.9%)
18	VAR00018- I am not in control of the success or failure I make of my life.	Neutral	3 (4.6%)
		Agree	51 (78.5%)
		Strongly Disagree	19 (29.2%)
19	VAR00019- I spend so long at my work that my outside relationships are suffering	Disagree	36 (55.4%)
		Neutral	2 (3.1%)
		Agree	8 (12.3%)
		Strongly Disagree	12 (18.5%)
20	VAR00020- My schedule is so demanding that I have little time to do things I enjoy.	Disagree	34 (52.3%)
		Neutral	11 (16.9%)
		Agree	8 (12.3%)
		Strongly Disagree	14 (21.5%)
21	VAR00021- Recently I have found it more difficult to control my emotions	Disagree	38 (58.5%)
		Neutral	10 (15.4%)
		Agree	3 (4.6%)
		Disagree	5 (7.7%)
22	VAR00022- I am clear about my responsibilities within and outside the organization	Agree	45 (69.2%)
		Strongly Agree	15 (23.1%)
		Disagree	18 (27.7%)
23	VAR00023- I have had physical problems such as headaches, insomnia, high blood pressure, fatigue etc.	Neutral	23 (35.4%)
		Agree	19 (29.2%)

		Strongly Agree	5 (7.7%)
		Strongly Disagree	29 (44.6%)
24	VAR00024- I wake up at night, thinking about things I need to do	Disagree	14 (21.5%)
		Neutral	17 (26.2%)
		Agree	5 (7.7%)
		Strongly Disagree	20 (30.8%)
25	VAR00025- I feel tension or pain when I am stressed, and have difficulty "getting over" my frustrations	Disagree	36 (55.4%)
		Neutral	7 (10.8%)
		Agree	2 (3.1%)
		Strongly Disagree	10 (15.4%)
26	VAR00026- There is not enough time to do everything I need to do.	Disagree	33 (50.8%)
		Neutral	14 (21.5%)
		Agree	8 (12.3%)
		Strongly Disagree	19 (29.2%)
27	VAR00027- I seem to have more things go wrong at once than others	Disagree	38 (58.5%)
		Neutral	8 (12.3%)
		Strongly Disagree	9 (13.8%)
28	VAR00028- I have often felt difficulties were piling up so high that I could not overcome them.	Disagree	47 (72.3%)
		Agree	9 (13.8%)

The first level is demographics where the population in the study consists of 52.3% male and 47.7% female. The majority of the population under study are Male. It is interesting to observe that there are equal numbers of people under the age groups of 25 to 30 years, 30 to 35 years, and Above 35 years. The population consists of 89.2% of members who are married and 10.8% of members who are unmarried people. The majority of the population under study are Married. The population consists of 16.9% Graduates and 83.1% Postgraduates, i.e. majority being postgraduates. The second level is organizational stressors where out of the total population, 50.8% believe that competitive pressures are a reason for stress within the organization. Out of the total population, 36.9% believe that Inability to voice complaints frustrates them. 47.7% of the population remains neutral regarding their job description being unrealistic. Furthermore, it is observed that no one in the extreme range Strongly Disagree or Strongly Agree. 52.3% of the total population disagrees with the fact that the communication within their organization is not effective. Also, it is observed that no one in the extreme range Strongly Disagree or Strongly Agree. Out of the total population, 75.4% disagree with brooding over the failure of a project over which they were working. Whereas no one has either Agreed or Strongly Agreed on the same. 76.9% of the members learn from the experience and move on to the next job if a project they are working on fails. It is interesting to observe that no employee disagrees with the same. 61.5% agree that they are affected by poor lighting, ventilation, and a crowded area which in turn causes interference with their work. The third level is group stressors where there are 64.6% of the population strongly agree that they have someone at work or outside it on whom they can confide in. 69.2% and 30.8% agree and strongly agree respectively on the lack of cohesiveness within the group which brings about difficulty in getting a particular job done. It is interesting to know that none disagree on the same. 41.5% of the population, neither agree nor disagree that ill will among the group members/ towards them causes stress, which is reflected in their work.

From the above distribution, we can interpret that 63.1% of the population feel that their respective group depends on them at work such that they have to do it all. It can be seen that 43.1% of the total population think that if others in their group would consider their opinion, then they would be able to solve most of the problems. Also, it can be seen that 72.3% disagree with having little patience with their co-workers. The fourth level is individual stressors where it can be interpreted that 78.5% population agrees that they are not in control of the success or failure they make of their life. From the above table, it can be interpreted that 55.4% population disagrees that their outside relationships are suffering due to long hours at work. From the above table, it can be interpreted that 52.3% population disagrees that they have little time to do things they enjoy due to their demanding schedule. From the above table, it can be interpreted that 58.5% population disagrees that they have difficulty controlling their emotions. From the above table, it can be interpreted that 69.2% population agree that they are clear about their responsibilities within and outside the Organization. 35.4% of the population neither agree nor disagree that they suffer from physical problems such as headaches, insomnia, high blood pressure, and fatigue. 44.6% of the population strongly disagree that they wake up at night thinking about things to do. 55.4% of the total population disagree that they are tensed or feel pain when they are stressed and also have difficulty "getting over" their frustrations. 50.8% of the total population disagree that they do not get enough time to do everything

they need to do. 58.5% of the total population disagree that they seem to have more things going wrong at once than others. 72.3% of the total population disagree that they have often felt difficulties piling up so high that they could not overcome them.

1.5 Findings and Discussion

It has been observed after the study that there are 34 and 31 males and females respectively, working in the company who are likely to suffer from stress.

Married members are more likely to suffer from stress than unmarried members.

Competitive pressures are a major reason for stress for the employees of the organization. Because of this, they have to put in long working hours and extra effort.

The members of the organization do not have any problems voicing their complaints. This shows that in this particular aspect, the company members are not stressed.

The members do not think that their job description is unrealistic which reduces their stress to a large extent. An unrealistic job description often leads to stress in an employee.

The communication within the organization is highly effective which relieves the members from stress.

From the analysis it can be seen that that even though the members may face failure it does not demoralize them and are not under stress.

It is seen that they learn from their failure and improve and move on to the next job even though they may have failed in a project they had undertaken.

Poor working conditions create a lot of stress within the organization as it is difficult to be working with poor lighting, no ventilation, and a crowded environment.

To relieve oneself of stress it has been observed that the members confide in someone they have within or outside the organization. This helps them to destress a lot.

Having a group that may have conflicts within themselves creates a lot of stress for the employees. The atmosphere of the working environment goes bad. Work is not done in an organized manner. It takes a lot of time to decide due to interpersonal conflicts.

Dependency of the group on a single individual creates a lot of stress for that particular individual. It increases the workload of the employee and to a certain extent, expectations also increase. But in the company, such is not the case to be seen.

The employees of the company work in coordination with one another therefore they don't suffer from having little patience with their coworkers.

It has been observed that the members agree to the fact that they are not in control of the success or failure that takes place in their lives. It is beyond their control.

Members at Times, even though they work for long hours and have to meet a lot of lines are good at keeping their relationships outside the organization.

Moreover, they do take some time off from their work to do things they enjoy doing.

The members do not have any difficulty in controlling their emotions due to any factor that may cause them to be under stress.

The members are clear about their responsibilities within and outside their organization. They are good at managing them both.

Some members do suffer from physical problems such as headaches, high BP, fatigue, etc. But because the environment of the organization is a healthy one therefore not many suffer from the problem.

The employees do not feel that they don't have time to do their personal or even professional work. They are systematic and do their work well in coordination with one another.

The members do not overburden themselves by piling up work for themselves.

1.6 Conclusion

It can be concluded that many people today work long hours, face constant deadlines, and are subject to pressure to produce more and more. Organizations and people who run them are under constant pressure to increase income while keeping costs in check. Especially industries meeting deadlines is a constant source of stress for the members. But through the research that has taken place it can be concluded that due to a good working environment and friendly atmosphere in the organization, the members are not too stressed.

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